

PSYCO-SOCIAL DISTRESS IN EMPLOYED VERSUS UNEMPLOYED PATIENTS WITH ADVANCED RENAL FAILURE

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Abstract

Objective: To compare the mean kidney disease and quality of life (KDQOL) score in employed versus unemployed patients with advanced renal failure

Study design: Cohort study.

Place and duration of study: Department of Nephrology, Combined Military Hospital, Multan for 6 months i.e. from 01 November 2024 till 30 April 2025.

Methodology: Sample size of 40 kidney disease patients were enrolled (20 employed and 20 unemployed). Patients were examined for psycho-social distress by using KDQOL scoring system and mental and physical stress level were recorded. All the data was analysed by using SPSS v.25.

Results: The mean age of patients in employed group was 48.45 ± 12.75 years, while in unemployed group was 39.45 ± 14.35 years. In employed group, there were 9 (45%) males while 11 (55%) females. In unemployed group, there were 12 (60%) males while 8 (40%) females. The mean total KDOL score was 112.45 ± 12.36 vs. 84.15 ± 17.75 in both groups, respectively, showing high score in employed group as compared to unemployed group ($p < 0.0001$). In employed group, 4 (20%) patients had distress while in unemployed group, 15 (75%) patients had distress.

Conclusion: Thus, quality of life and mental health of hemodialysis patients, who were unemployed as well was poorer than employed patients. This is issue of concern for financial support as renal failure treatment is a life-long therapy until transplant.

INTRODUCTION

When signs of kidney damage, such as decreased glomerular filtration rate (GFR) or proteinuria, have been present for more than three months, chronic kidney disease (CKD) is diagnosed. The urine albumin: creatinine ratio and GFR are used to categorize it. Eleven percent of adults worldwide suffer from chronic kidney disease (CKD), and the prevalence increases dramatically with age.^{1,2} Adults having chronic hypertension, diabetes, being female, or older

age group, and members of racial minorities are more likely to have CKD.^{2,3} An even greater burden than previously thought is shown by the expanding body of research on the prevalence of CKD.⁴

In many South Asian and Central American nations, chronic kidney disease (CKD) of uncertain aetiology is a significant emerging public health concern. Therefore, although while diabetes and hypertension are still the main risk factors for chronic kidney disease

(CKD), the multifaceted character of the disease is becoming more well acknowledged, as is the fact that CKD exacerbates a number of other health issues, including hypertension.^{5, 6} For patients with end-stage renal failure, hemodialysis is a proven replacement therapy. However, it significantly affects the patient's quality of life.⁷ Patients' physical, social, psychological, and emotional well-being are all negatively impacted by chronic dialysis, which frequently results in anxiety, sadness, restless legs syndrome, post-dialysis exhaustion, and generalized weakness. This has a significant impact on patients' health-related quality of life (HRQOL).^{8, 9} Because only 40% of ESRD patients in Pakistan have access to dialysis services, 67% of them receive insufficient dialysis (2 sessions per week) and are considered under-dialyzed, the quality of life for these patients is thought to be lower than in other nations. Patients who receive insufficient dialysis have a worse survival rate (40.5%) and a lower QOL.^{7, 10}

Rationale of study was to compare the mean kidney disease and quality of life (KDQOL) score in employed versus unemployed patients with advanced renal failure. Literature showed that quality of life of unemployed patients is more disturbed than employed ones. This could be due to physical health issues and hemodialysis schedules that result in unemployment. However, little research has been done in the past because there is no evidence in local literature. Therefore, the purpose of this study was to gather information regarding the effectiveness of job status for patients with renal failure, particularly those receiving hemodialysis.

METHODOLOGY

This cohort study was carried out in the Department of Nephrology, Combined Military Hospital, Multan for 6 months i.e. from 01 November 2024 till 30 April 2025 after approval from the hospital's Ethical Review Committee. With a 95% confidence level, 80% study power, and a mean KDQOL score of 48.59 ± 9.81 for employed patients and 38.94 ± 11.05 for jobless patients, the sample size of 40 cases—20 in each

group—is determined.¹¹ After the children were screened for the following criteria, all patients were enrolled using a non-probability, consecutive sampling technique:

Inclusion: Patients of age 20-70 years, both genders, diagnosed with advanced stage renal failure we enrolled. Advanced renal failure was defined as presence of Glomerular Filtration Rate (GFR) $< 15 \text{ mL/min/1.73}$ and need hemodialysis for fluid overload and uremia.

Exclusion: Patients with psychiatric problems or taking medicines for psychiatric diseases including schizophrenia, post-transplant patients were excluded from the study.

Informed consent was obtained after explaining them the pros and cons of research. Demographics (name, age, sex, BMI, duration of renal failure, lifestyle, socioeconomic status and residence, education level, diabetes, hypertension, ischemic heart disease) were noted. Then patients were divided in two groups depends on employment status. In group E, patients with employment will be placed. In group U, patients with unemployment will be placed. Then patients will be interviewed by psychiatrist by using Kidney Disease Quality of Life (KDQOL-36™) scale. The 36-item KDQOL scale is used to evaluate the health-related quality of life of dialysis patients with advanced renal failure. The Physical Component Summary (PCS), Mental Component Summary (MCS), Burden of Kidney Disease (BKD), Symptoms and Problems of Kidney Disease (SPKD), and Effect of Kidney Disease (EKD) are the five subscales that make up this tool. The latter three subscales evaluate concerns unique to individuals with ESRD or CKD [24 questions total], while the first two subscales are general assessments of Health-Related Quality of Life (HRQOL) [12 items total]. The KDQOL-36 kidney-targeted scales are assessed by averaging the scale's items and linearly translating each item to a range of 0–100. Better quality of life is indicated by high scores. $\text{KDQOL} < 50$ was considered as distress. SF-36 was also used to check distress level. All this information was recorded on Proforma.

Figure-1: Flow Chart (n= 40)

SPSS version 25 was used to enter and analyze the data. Categorical variables were shown as F (%) and numerical data as mean and SD. The independent samples t-test and the chi-square test were used to compare the two groups' mean KDQOL scores and distress, respectively. A P-value of less than 0.05 was considered significant.

RESULTS

In this study, we enrolled total 40 patients with advanced stage renal failure. The mean age of patients in employed group was 48.45 ± 12.75 years, while in unemployed group was 39.45 ± 14.35 years. In employed group, there were 9 (45%) males while 11 (55%) females. In unemployed group, there were 12 (60%) males while 8 (40%) females. In employed group, there were 6 (30%) obese and in unemployed group, there were 10 (50%) obese patients. The mean duration of renal failure in employed group was 5.60 ± 3.4 years, while in unemployed group was 5.10 ± 4.34 years. In employed group, about 8 (40%) had sedentary lifestyle while in unemployed group, 11 (55%) had sedentary

lifestyle. Mostly individual belonged to low socioeconomic class. In employed group, about 50% cases were coming from rural area while in unemployed group, 9 (45%) were residing in urban areas. In employed group, 16 (80%) patients had diabetes, 19 (95%) had hypertension and 13 (65%) had ischemic heart disease. In unemployed group, 15 (75%) patients had diabetes, 16 (80%) had hypertension and 8 (40%) had ischemic heart disease. Table-I

In employed group, the mean symptoms score of patients was 36.95 ± 8.47, while in unemployed group was 26.30 ± 8.86. The mean effects of kidney disease was observed as 35.50 ± 6.93 vs. 27.85 ± 10.17 in both groups, respectively, showing high score with employed as compared to unemployed group (p<0.0001). The mean burden of kidney disease score was 40.00 ± 5.69 in employed group and to 30.00 ± 6.51 in unemployed group. The mean total KDOL score was 112.45 ± 12.36 vs. 84.15 ± 17.75 in both groups, respectively, showing high score in employed group as compared to unemployed group (p<0.0001). The mean SF-36 physical

score was 16.15 ± 3.36 in employed group and to 13.75 ± 2.34 in unemployed group, showing better physical health in employed patients ($p < 0.0001$). The mean SF-36 mental score was 17.95 ± 4.01 in employed group and to $12.85 \pm$

3.27 in unemployed group, showing better mental health in employed patients ($p < 0.0001$). In employed group, 4 (20%) patients had distress while in unemployed group, 15 (75%) patients had distress. Table-II

Table-I: Baseline information of renal failure patients included in the study (n = 40)

	Group	
	Employed	Unemployed
n	20	20
Age, in years	48.45 ± 12.75	39.45 ± 14.35
20-45 years	9 (45%)	14 (70%)
46-70 years	11 (55%)	6 (30%)
Gender		
Male	9 (45%)	12 (60%)
Female	11 (55%)	8 (40%)
BMI	22.45 ± 3.61	24.30 ± 3.47
Obese	6 (30%)	10 (50%)
Non-obese	14 (70%)	10 (50%)
Duration of renal failure and hemodialysis, in years	5.60 ± 3.4	5.10 ± 4.34
Less than 5 years	10 (50%)	13 (65%)
6-10 years	8 (40%)	6 (30%)
More than 10 years	2 (10%)	1 (5.0%)
Lifestyle		
Sedentary	8 (40%)	11 (55%)
Active	12 (60%)	9 (45%)
Socioeconomic status		
Low	11 (55%)	8 (40%)
Middle	9 (45%)	12 (60%)
High	Nil	Nil
Residence		
Rural	10 (50%)	9 (45%)
Urban	10 (50%)	11 (55%)
Education		
Educated	14 (70%)	12 (60%)
Uneducated	6 (30%)	8 (40%)
History of		
Diabetes	16 (80%)	15 (75%)
Hypertension	19 (95%)	16 (80%)
Ischemic heart disease	13 (65%)	8 (40%)

Table-II: Comparison of KDQOL assessment in both groups (n = 40)

	Group		p-value
	Employed	Unemployed	
n	20	20	
Symptoms score	36.95 ± 8.47	26.30 ± 8.86	< 0.0001
Effects of Kidney disease	35.50 ± 6.93	27.85 ± 10.17	0.008

Burden of kidney disease	40.00 ± 5.69	30.00 ± 6.51	<0.0001
Total score	112.45 ± 12.36	84.15 ± 17.75	<0.0001
SF-36 physical scale	16.15 ± 3.36	13.75 ± 2.34	0.012
SF-36 Mental scale	17.95 ± 4.01	12.85 ± 3.27	<0.0001
Distress	4 (20%)	15 (75%)	<0.0001

DISCUSSION

In this study, the mean total KDOL score was 112.45 ± 12.36 vs. 84.15 ± 17.75 in both groups, respectively, showing high score in employed group as compared to unemployed group (p<0.0001). In employed group, 4 (20%) patients had distress while in unemployed group, 15 (75%) patients had distress.

According to Bay et al., patients with advanced chronic kidney disease (CKD) had mean percentages of work impairment of 24.35 ± 15.23 and face absenteeism of 13.36 ± 32.34. Additionally, compared to patients who were employed, those who were unemployed had poor mental and physical composites (p<0.01) and considerable subjective symptoms and issue lists, impacts, and burden of renal disease (p<0.01).¹¹ These findings were comparable to those of Van Haalen et al., who found that patients with advanced chronic kidney disease had a mean percentage of 33 for overall work impairment and a mean percentage of 10 for absenteeism.¹²

In a similar vein, Ahmed et al. discovered that patients with greater levels of education had better quality of life because they were better able to follow their healthcare team's instructions and safety measures.⁷ Another study carried out in Pakistan by Anees et al. revealed similar findings. Employed patients had better work status (54.69 ± 34.45 vs. 17.33 ± 27.87, p = 0.01) and social functioning ability (68.36 ± 25.60 vs. 53.83 ± 23.87, p = 0.027), but they also had higher kidney disease symptoms (83.53 ± 10.62 vs. 77.38 ± 15.16, p = 0.05) and effects (74.41 ± 17.86 vs. 63.58 ± 21.22, p = 0.015).¹³ Patients who work are self-sufficient and self-sufficient, which gives them confidence and security when receiving care. Employed patients' daily pattern of going to work and spending time with their coworkers keeps them occupied and socially engaged, which enhances their QOL.¹⁴

¹⁵ However, because they are busy all day, employed patients experience greater pain and

disease symptoms than unemployed patients. Unemployed patients, on the other hand, experience less pain, fewer disease symptoms, and greater social functioning because they have nothing to do and are free all day to engage with friends, family, and relatives.^{16,17}

Another aspect influencing hemodialysis patients' QOL is their ethnicity. According to Ahmed et al., Peshawari patients had a 16% greater quality of life and a 22% worse physical health than patients from other ethnic groups.⁷ Other ethnic groups, with the exception of Peshawari, may have lower QOL scores because of patient beliefs, perceptions of the disease, and comprehension of treatment options, all of which have a direct impact on the patients' psychological well-being.^{18,19}

Although it is sometimes disregarded, the quality of life for patients with advanced CKD is an important factor to take into account when assessing total medical care. The findings demonstrated that patients without jobs had a lower quality of life than those with jobs. Their career prospects were hampered by their symptoms, illness burden, and physical and mental condition. On the other hand, patients who were able to continue working had an HRQOL that was far less affected by their kidney condition.^{20,21}

Even though the KDQOL-36 is widely used, efforts are still needed to help interpret the results. By offering reference values for the entire dialysis population in the United States as well as for specific subgroups, this study increases our understanding of how to interpret KDQOL-36 scales. Furthermore, the KDQOL-36 Summary Score scale, a new KDQOL-36 composite, showed outstanding dependability and made it simple to include patient-reported outcomes into research investigations and clinical practice.^{22,23}

Due to time constraints, we only looked at KDQOL in this experiment; a few other factors may also have an impact on CKD patients'

physical and mental well-being. Nonetheless, more aspects might be taken into account. Sample size for this study was also very small. However, more research with a large sample size is advised.

CONCLUSION

We observed that quality of life and mental health of hemodialysis patients, who were unemployed as well as poorer than employed patients. This is issue of concern for financial support as renal failure treatment is a life-long therapy until transplant. Thus, in future, we may consider some cost-effective treatment protocols for long-term treatment plan to reduce financial burden and also to improve physical and mental health of such patients. This would contribute to the advancement of our understanding and the updating of future treatment protocols to improve QOL and reduce financial burden from patients.

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